

Oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by imidazolium fluorochromate in non-aqueous media – A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by imidazolium fluorochromate (IFC) have been studied in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO). The main product of oxidation is carbon dioxide. The reaction is first order with respect to IFC and organic acids. The reaction is acid catalyzed and the acid dependence has the form : $k_{obs} = a + b [H^+]$. The oxidation of α -deuterio formic acid exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.63$ at 303 K). The reaction has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents and solvent effect analyzed using Kamlet-Taft and Swain's multi parametric equations. The temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect indicates the presence of a symmetrical cyclic transition state in the rate determining step.

Keywords : Imidazolium fluorochromate, solvent effect, kinetics, oxidation.

Introduction

The influence of solvent on the rate of any reaction can be described in terms of solvation which is a stabilization process. Two basic view points have been established on the solvation phenomenon. According to the first, a solvent is considered as a homogeneous continuum which surrounds the solute molecules and exerts long range interactions. The strength of these interactions with the solute molecules is described in terms of macroscopic physical properties of the solvent like dielectric constant (ϵ) and refractive index (η). According to the second view point, a solvent is considered to be anisotropic and inhomogeneous molecules. These forces are chemical in nature and result in the formation of solvation complexes through donor-acceptor bonds which are localized and direct in space. The strength of these interactions is described in terms of solvation parameters, namely, hydrogen bond donor acidity (α) and hydrogen bond acceptor basicity (β) etc. Thus the solvent can solvate the solute by exhibiting any of these interactions with the specific sites in the solute. Hence the effect of solvent on the rate of

the reaction can be described in terms of a multi parametric equation which involves different solvation parameters. We have studied the solvent effect of the oxidation of formic acid in 19 different protic and aprotic solvents.

A variety of compounds containing chromium(VI) have proved to be versatile reagents capable of oxidizing almost every oxidizable functional group¹. A number of new chromium(VI) containing compounds, with heterocyclic bases, like pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC)², pyridinium bromochromate (PBC)³, quinolinium chlorochromate (QCC)⁴, benzimidazolium fluorochromate (BIFC)⁵, quinolinium bromochromate (QBC)⁶, imidazolium fluorochromate (IFC)⁷, pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC)⁸, tributylammonium chlorochromate (TriBACC)⁹, tripropylammonium fluorochromate (TriPAFC)¹⁰, quinolinium fluorochromate (QFC)¹¹ and imidazolium dichromate (IDC)¹² have been developed to improve the selectivity of oxidation of organic compounds. The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by various oxidants have been reported¹³⁻¹⁹. However, the kinetics of oxidation of formic and oxalic

acids by IFC, a Cr^{VI} reagent has not yet been studied. This prompted us to undertake the present investigation. The present work reports the kinetics of oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by IFC and evaluates the reaction constants. Mechanistic aspects are also discussed.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometric analysis :

To determine the stoichiometry, an excess of IFC ($\times 10$ or greater) reacted with the organic acid in DMSO (100 cm³) and the amount of residual IFC after completion of reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at 363 nm. The results indicated 1 : 1 stoichiometry. No quantitative determination of carbon dioxide formed was carried out. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method was 3.95 ± 0.25 .

Order of reaction :

The reactions were found to be first order with respect to IFC. The individual kinetic runs were strictly first order to IFC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants do not depend on the initial concentration of IFC. The reaction rate increases with an increase in the concentration of organic acids (Table 1). Linear plots of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log [\text{Organic acid}]$ with unit slope demonstrates the first order dependence of the rate on $[\text{Organic acid}]$.

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile :

The oxidation of organic acids by IFC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerization of

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of organic acids by [IFC] in DMSO at 303 K

10 ³ [IFC] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ² [Organic acid] (mol dm ⁻³)	10 ⁵ k_{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
		Formic acid	Oxalic acid
0.5	2.0	0.92	4.08
1.0	2.0	0.99	4.18
1.5	2.0	0.96	4.10
2.0	2.0	0.95	4.08
2.5	2.0	0.98	4.14
3.0	2.0	0.93	4.12
1.0	1.0	0.50	2.04
1.0	1.5	0.72	3.12
1.0	2.5	1.20	5.18
1.0	3.0	1.46	6.20
1.0	3.5	1.70	7.24
1.0	4.0	1.98	8.20
1.0	2.0	0.91 ^a	4.06 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

acrylonitrile. Further, an addition of a radical scavenger, acrylonitrile, has no effect on the rate (Table 1). Thus, a one-electron oxidation giving rise to free radicals is unlikely.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The kinetics of oxidation of organic acid was studied at four different temperatures viz. 298, 303, 308 and 313 K. The second order rate constants were calculated (Table 2). The Arrhenius plot of $\log k_2$ versus $1/T$ is found to be linear. The enthalpy of activation, entropy of activation and free energy of activation were calculated from k_2 at 298, 303, 308 and 313 K using the Eyring relationship by the method of least square and presented in Table 2. The entropy of activation is negative for organic acid. The negative entropy of activation in conjunction with other experimental data supports the mechanism outlined in Schemes 1 and 2.

Table 2. Activation parameters and second order rate constants for the oxidation of organic acids by IFC in DMSO

Substrate	10 ⁴ $\times k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K			
Oxalic acid	12.54	20.90	32.00	48.6	67.13 \pm 1.5	75.08 \pm 5	89.87 \pm 3
Formic acid	3.28	4.95	7.62	12.04	64.64 \pm 1.3	95.11 \pm 4	93.43 \pm 3
DFA	0.55	0.88	1.38	2.20	68.91 \pm 1.0	95.29 \pm 2	97.69 \pm 2
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	5.96	5.63	5.52	5.47			

[Organic acid] = 2.0×10^{-2} M; [IFC] = 1.0×10^{-3} M.

Scheme 1. Mechanism of oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by IFC acid-independent path

Effect of acidity :

The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions (Table 3). The hydrogen ion dependence has the following form :

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+] \quad (3)$$

The values of *a* and *b*, for oxalic acid at 303 K are $6.86 \pm 0.45 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $27.90 \pm 0.89 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.997$). The corresponding values

Table 3. Dependence of the reaction rate on hydrogen ion concentration for the oxidation of organic acids by IFC in DMSO at 303 K

Organic acid	at [TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)							
	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8
$10^5 k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$	101	127	153	176	201	230	266	300
Oxalic acid	5	10	6.40	7.72	9.02	10.52	12.04	13.70
Formic acid	16	20	24	28	32	36	40	44

[Organic acid] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, [IFC] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$

for the oxidation of formic acid at 303 K are $3.24 \pm 0.29 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $15.18 \pm 0.58 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.997$).

The observed hydrogen ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent another acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of IFC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile.

The formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species as earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PCC²⁰ and PFC²¹.

Kinetic isotope effect :

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of α -

Scheme 2. Mechanism of oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by IFC : acid-dependent path.

deuterio formic acid (DFA) was studied. Results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2).

Solvent-reactivity correlation :

The Kamlet-Taft method for the examination of solvent effect :

In order to obtain a deeper insight into the various solvent-solvent-solute interactions, which influence reactivity, the solvatochromic comparison method developed by Kamlet²² has been used. This method may be used to unravel, quantify, correlate and rationalize multiple interacting solvent effects on reactivity. The kinetic data were correlated with the solvatochromic parameters α , β and π^* characteristic of different solvents in the form of following LSER :

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (5)$$

where π^* is an index of solvent dipolarity/polarizability, which measures the ability of the solvent to stabilize a charge or a dipole by virtue of its dielectric effect, α is the solvent HBD (hydrogen bond donor) acidity, β is the solvent HBA (hydrogen bond acceptor) basicity of the

solvent in a solute to solvent hydrogen bond and A_0 is the intercept term.

The oxidation of formic acid was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvent was limited due to the solubility of IFC and its reaction with formic acid. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are given in Table 4.

The rate constants of oxidation, k_2 , in 18 solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship eq. (5) of Kamlet *et al.*²². It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α .

Kamlet *et al.*²³ established that the effect of a solvent on the reaction rate should be given in terms of the following properties : (i) the behaviour of the solvent as a dielectric, facilitating the separation of opposite charges in the transition state, (ii) the ability of the solvent to donate a proton in a solvent-to-solute hydrogen bond and thus stabilize the anion in transition state and (iii) the

Table 4. Second order rate constants for the oxidation of formic acid by IFC at 303 K in various solvents

Solvents	$k_2 \cdot 10^5$ ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Solvents	$k_2 \cdot 10^5$ ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
Chloroform	15.4	Toluene	2.70
1,2-Dichloroethane	13.9	Acetophenone	15.50
Dichloromethane	15.7	THF	4.80
DMSO	49.5	<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	6.44
Acetone	11.0	1,4-Dioxane	5.66
DMF	24.9	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	2.68
Butanone	8.1	Carbon disulfide	1.12
Nitrobenzene	17.7	Acetic acid	3.82
Benzene	3.11	Ethyl acetate	3.78
Cyclohexane	0.20		

[Formic acid] = $2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$; [IFC] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

ability of the solvent to donate an electron pair. The parameter π^* is an appropriate measure of the first property, while the second and third properties are governed by the parameters α and β respectively. The solvent parameters (π^* , α and β) are taken from the literature²² and are given in Table 5. The linear dependence (LSER) on the solvent properties were used to correlate and predict a wide variety of solvent effect.

In order to explain the kinetic results through the sol-

vent polarity and basicity or acidity, the rate constants were correlated with the solvatochromic parameters π^* , α and β using total solvatochromic equation, eq. (5). The correlation of kinetic data were realized by means of multiple linear regression analysis. It was found that the rate constants in 19 solvents showed satisfactory correlation with the π^* , α and β solvent parameters. The results of correlation analysis in terms of eq. (5), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β are given below in eqs. (6)–(9).

Table 5. Solvent parameters²²

Solvent	π^*	α	β
Chloroform	0.58	0.44	0.00
1,2-Dichloroethane	0.81	0.00	0.00
Dichloromethane	0.82	0.30	0.00
DMSO	1.00	0.00	0.76
Acetone	0.71	0.08	0.48
DMF	0.88	0.00	0.69
Butanone	0.67	0.06	0.48
Nitrobenzene	1.01	0.00	0.39
Benzene	0.59	0.00	0.10
Cyclohexane	0.00	0.00	0.00
Toluene	0.54	0.00	0.11
Acetophenone	0.90	–	0.49
THF	0.58	0.00	0.55
<i>tert</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.41	0.68	1.01
1,4-Dioxane	0.55	0.00	0.37
1,2-Dimethoxyethane	0.53	0.00	0.41
Carbon disulfide	–	–	–
Acetic acid	0.64	1.12	–
Ethyl acetate	0.55	0.00	0.45

$$\log k_2 = -5.22 + (1.92 \pm 0.20) \pi^* + (0.13 \pm 0.15) \beta + (0.40 \pm 0.16) \alpha \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8656; SD = 0.11; n = 18; \psi = 0.35$$

$$\log k_2 = -5.08 + (1.84 \pm 0.15) \pi^* + (0.27 \pm 0.12) \beta \quad (7)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8644; SD = 0.10; n = 18; \psi = 0.28$$

$$\log k_2 = -5.06 + (1.9 \pm 0.19) \pi^* \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8828; SD = 0.11; n = 18; \psi = 0.24$$

$$\log k_2 = -5.60 + (0.60 \pm 0.38) \beta \quad (9)$$

$$r^2 = 0.1179; SD = 0.35; n = 18; \psi = 0.88$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter²⁴.

Kamlet's triparametric equation²² explains *ca.* 86% of the effect of solvation on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion²⁴ the correlation is not even satisfactory (*cf.* eq. (9)). The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 88% of the data. Both α and β play relatively minor roles.

The Swain's method for the examination of solvent effect :

The data on solvent effect were analyzed in terms of Swain's equation²⁵ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (10)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A+B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analyzed in terms of eq. (10), separately with A and B and with $(A+B)$.

$$\log k_2 = (1.54 \pm 0.03) A + (1.81 \pm 0.02) B - 5.72 \quad (11)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9879; SD = 0.14; n = 19; \psi = 0.22$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.21 (\pm 0.49) A - 4.50 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.2105; SD = 0.08; n = 19; \psi = 0.88$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.70 (\pm 0.16) B - 5.28 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7019; SD = 0.19; n = 19; \psi = 0.35$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.72 \pm 0.16 (A + B) - 5.72 \quad (14)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9776; SD = 0.28; n = 19; \psi = 0.07$$

The rates of oxidation of formic acid in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation solvation alone accounts for *ca.* 70% of the data. The correlation with anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 97% of the data.

Mechanism :

In view of the absence of any effect of acrylonitrile on the rate of the reaction and failure to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile, it is unlikely that a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is operative in this reaction. The presence of a substantial kinetic isotopic effect confirmed that the α -C-H bond is cleaved in the rate determining step. The observed solvent effect also indicates that the transition state of the reaction is more polar than the reactants.

For the formic acid oxidation, the cation-solvating power of the solvents plays a relatively more important role, supporting the proposition that an electron-deficient carbon center is formed in the transition state. Thus, the

transfer of a hydride ion from the acid to the oxidant is indicated. This hydride ion transfer may take place either via an anhydride or by an acyclic process. The involvement of a concerted cyclic process is supported by a study of the temperature dependence of the kinetic isotope effect²⁶. The data for protio- and deuterio-formic acids when fitted in the familiar expression $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(-\Delta H^*/RT)$ show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state in which the differences in the activation energies for the protio and deuterio compounds are equal to the differences in the zero point energies of the corresponding C-H and C-D bonds ($\approx 4.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) and the entropies of activation of respective reactions are almost equal^{27,28}. Similar phenomena were observed earlier in the oxidation of diols by BPCC²⁹ and of benzhydrol by PFC³⁰.

Cogent evidence against the occurrence of a concerted one-step bimolecular process by hydrogen transfer has been documented and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic bimolecular process. It is well established that intrinsically the concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterized by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer. It has also been shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI} , involves six-electrons and being a Hückel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus, a transition state having a planar, cyclic and symmetrical structure can be envisaged for the decomposition of the ester intermediate. An overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and then decomposition of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the products (Schemes 1 and 2).

The observed negative value of entropy of activation also support the proposed mechanism. As the charge separation takes place in the transition state, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy.

The mechanism depicted in Scheme 1 leads to the following equation :

$$\text{Rate} = kK [\text{Organic acid}] [\text{IFC}] \quad (19)$$

It can be shown that

$$[\text{IFC}] = [\text{IFC}]_T / (1 + K [\text{Organic acid}]) \quad (20)$$

Therefore,

$$-d[\text{IFC}]/dt = kK [\text{Organic acid}] [\text{IFC}]_T / (1 + K [\text{Organic acid}]) \quad (21)$$

Since the reaction is the first order with respect to each the organic acid and IFC, one can assume that $1 \gg K [\text{Organic acid}]$. The assumption is made because the concentration of organic acid is in the order of 0.001 to 0.002 mol dm⁻³ and which is very small compared with 1. The eq (22) can therefore, be written as

$$-d[\text{IFC}]/dt = kK [\text{Organic acid}] [\text{IFC}] \quad (22)$$

This rate equation is in accord with the experimental results

The observed dependence on the hydrogen-ion concentration in the reaction shows that there is an additional acid-catalyzed pathway. The acid-dependent path way is given in Scheme 2.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

The α -deuterio formic acid (DCOOH or DFA) was prepared by the reported method³¹. Due to non-aqueous nature of the medium, *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in a polar solvents like DMSO it is likely to be completely ionized. Solvents were purified by the usual literature methods.

Preparation of imidazolium fluorochromate :

40% Hydrofluoric acid (11.3 mL, 0.23 mol) was added dropwise to imidazole (13.62 g, 0.2 mol) cooled in ice in a polythene beaker with constant stirring. A clear solution was obtained within 5 min. Dry and well powdered chromium trioxide (20 g, 0.2 mol) was added to this solution slowly with stirring. The resulting mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 30 min and left overnight in a refrigerator. Bright red orange crystals of IFC formed were separated by filtration and dried *in vacuo* for 2–3 h. The reagent IFC, can be stored in a polythene container without appreciable loss in its activity³². Yield 85%, m.p. 126–128 °C. Its purity was checked by the iodometric method

Kinetic measurements

The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the organic acids over IFC. The temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 K. The solvent was DMSO unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of IFC spectrophotometrically at 363 nm by using Shimadzu UV/VISIBLE spectrophotometer with recording facilities for up to 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear plots of $\log [\text{IFC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$. Data analysis were performed using Microcal origin (version 6.0) computer software. The goodness of the fit is discussed using the correlation coefficients and standard deviation

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